

PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF

IMPLEMENTATION OF STEM EDUCATION IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN.

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Annotation. This article gives a broad idea of the psychological and pedagogical conditions for the implementation of STEM education for students.

Keywords: STEAM, STEM education, psychological, modern education, subjectivity, construction, design.

Аннотация: Данная статья дает широкое представление о психолого-педагогических условиях реализации STEM-образования студентов.

Ключевые слова: STEAM, STEM-образование, психология, современное образование, субъектность, конструкция, проектирование.

STEAM-approach education appeared in the United States, and today it is introduced at the level of state programs in countries aimed at increasing their scientific and technical elite.

STEAM education in Russia is currently developing very fast, primarily as extracurricular education. Initially, programs for children of preschool and elementary school age were partially developed and provided with a modern educational science environment for the implementation of STEAM pedagogy tasks.

This Program is modular and consists of five independent and interconnected modules:

1. didactic systems;
2. conducting experiments with theoretical and practical natural phenomena;
3. LEGO construction;
4. mathematical development;
5. robotics.

Each module consists of materials provided with methodological equipment and specially developed topics. The program corresponds to the Federal State Educational Standard. It is based on the principles of strengthening child development, supporting the diversity of childhood, preserving the uniqueness and inner value of childhood as an

important stage. In the general development of the person, personality development and humanism, the nature of the interaction between adults and children, respect, the personality of the child, the implementation of the Program in its own forms is carried out based on the characteristics of the age.

The implementation of STEAM education in preschool education and upbringing is considered the most urgent, in which children understand nature, the formation of a creative approach, the formation of inventiveness by teaching the engineering approach, the scaling of logical and critical thinking, the understanding and application of scientific methods, the basics of design and construction. gives an opportunity to understand.

It is advisable to start the implementation of STEAM education mainly from 4-year-old children, because from this age children's thinking begins to develop. Even children who do not go to preschool education organizations can see the cases of making different things from clay (pets, cars, household appliances, trees, etc.). That's why you can see that children try to make things out of clay and imitate them.

In pre-school educational organizations, we can see that they make things based on specific plans. In this, children learn to make different things from plasticine or LEGO toys. During this period, the implementation of STAEM education helps the child to develop creativity and logical thinking.

The many benefits and relevance of STEM education are evident today. But there are significant problems in developing "mastery" of this practical and progressive system. It can be seen that the most important aspect of the implementation of the program "STEM education for children of preschool and primary school age" is the need to improve the psychological and pedagogical skills of teachers.

A child's self-awareness and creativity are related to the formation of the subjectivity of a preschool child. However, the concept of "subjectivity" remains difficult for teachers to understand. To understand the extent to which STEM learning tasks exist for a preschool child, the age-normative model of child development helps us to identify favorable and unfavorable conditions for normal development [3].

Knowing the age norm not only helps to work with them adequately. Also, the age-normative model of development is a pedagogical interpretation of the psychological

concept of the norm of development and analyzes the formation of subjectivity from generality in the mind. A child's activity is manifested in the presence of a clear intention. It is based on the desire of the teacher to use the appropriate material on the child and record the final result, to independently select samples and copy different materials.

A preschooler is curious about things and events around him. what for? What is this? Asks questions like In explaining them, it is important to teach by organizing specific materials (maps, diagrams, icons, stories, pictures, etc.) based on facts and simple causality [1].

Children can choose different professions. Here are some important points to consider:

First, the child should be interested in his future work and not in the interest of relatives or acquaintances;

Secondly, you need to explain everything to the child when choosing a job, that professions require certain activities, thinking and abilities;

Thirdly, Future activity should match personal characteristics.

After that, subjectivity develops in the child's mind, experiences related to self-awareness, feelings and relationships with other people. During this period, prototypes of natural phenomena, the formation of the worldview, the worldview, and the first ideas about the world of people are formed. STEM education is the most desirable approach to the norm of preschool child development, and the principles of this educational system naturally solve age-related developmental problems.

The child is the most active researcher, experimenter. Many special psychological studies show that a 3-5 year old child can create new ideas, shapes and designs. trained engineer. With a well-organized educational process, children's interest in understanding this natural world can be transformed into technical creativity, as well as instilling interest in the profession they can take in the future[2;4].

In conclusion, the implementation of STEAM education in preschool education and upbringing is considered the most urgent, in which children's understanding of nature, the formation of a creative approach, training in the engineering approach, and the scaling

of critical thinking, the understanding and application of scientific methods at a young age. are the pedagogical conditions of the psychological concept of normative norms.

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